

D5.4

Pilot Demonstrators (M35)

WODR

D5.4

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Revision **V1.0**

Work package	WP5
Task	T5.4
Due date	31-01-2026
Submission date	31-01-2026
Deliverable lead	WODR
Version	V1.0
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Abstract

This deliverable presents the **final version of the DATAMITE pilot demonstrators**, including the completed deployment, integration, and validation of the DATAMITE framework across all pilot environments. It consolidates the outcomes of the second pilot iteration and confirms the framework's readiness for exploitation and replication beyond the project's lifetime.

Keywords

pilots, demonstrator, validation, integration, components, framework, tests, validations

Document revision history

Version	Date	Description of change	Contributor(s)
v0.1	20-10-2025	1 st version of deliverable	Anna Rzeszutko (WODR)
v0.11	15-12-2025	1 st version of deliverable – fixes and explanations	Adam Fojud (WODR)
v0.12	16-12-2025	1 st version of deliverable – Pilot 4 text integration	Pedro Boto (E-REDES)
v0.2	21-01-2026	1 st Internal review version	Adam Fojud (WODR)
v0.3	23-01-2026	1 st Internal review version Ready	Vasileios Siopidis (CERTH) Daniel Grafen (FhG)
v0.4	25-01-2026	1 st Internal review version - revised	Adam Fojud (WODR)
V1.0	29-01-2026	Final version of deliverable	Adam Fojud (WODR)

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Project co-funded by the European Commission in the Horizon Europe Programme

Nature of the deliverable

DEM

Dissemination level

PU Public, fully open. e.g., website

✓

CL Classified information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC

SEN Confidential to DATAMITE project and Commission Services

* Deliverable types:

R: document, report (excluding periodic and final reports).

DEM: demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs.

DEC: websites, patent filings, press and media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: software, technical diagrams, etc.

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Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIoD	Artificial Intelligence on Demand
AIM	Agriculture Information Model
API	Application Programming Interface
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
CI/CD	Continuous Integration / Continuous Delivery
CPU	Central Processing Unit
DPC	Data Processing Centre
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
DB	Database
DBMS	Database Management System
DIH	Digital Innovation Hubs
DNS	Domain Name System
EC	European Commission
EDC	Eclipse Data Connector
EDIH	European Digital Innovation Hub
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable principles
FMS	Farm Management System
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GA	Grant Agreement
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
IaaS	Infrastructure as a Service
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
ML	Machine Learning
NFT	Non-Fungible Token
OLAP	Online Analytical Processing
OLTP	Online Transaction Processing
PaaS	Platform as a Service
PPP	Plant Protection Products
RAM	Random-Access Memory
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol

SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
SSL	Secure Sockets Layer
UDRG	User Defined Rules Generator
VM	Virtual Machine
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

DATAMITE is a project funded by the European Commission as part of the Horizon Europe program and coordinated by the ITI - Technological Institute of Informatics. DATAMITE empowers European companies by delivering a modular, open-source and multi-domain framework to improve DATA Monetizing, Interoperability, Trading and Exchange, in the form of software modules, training, and business materials.

DATAMITE unleashes the potential of monetisation at two levels. At internal level, users will have tools to improve quality management of their data, the adherence to FAIR principles, and their ability to upskill on technical and business aspects thanks to the multiple open-source training materials the project will generate. Therefore, data will become trustworthy and more reliable also in other paradigms like AI.

At the external level, keeping users in control of their data will provide new sources of revenue and interaction with other stakeholders. The architecture envisioned for DATAMITE enables DIHs sandboxing, becoming a potential facilitator in onboarding SMEs and low-tech SMEs into the data economy. Together, DATAMITE's solutions will function as a catalyst to boost data monetisation in the European productive fabric.

1.1 Deliverable Purpose and Scope

Specifically, the Grant Agreement states the following regarding this Deliverable:

Final version of the demonstrators.

Hence, the purpose of this document is to present the **final integration and validation** of the key components of the DATAMITE framework and to confirm the system's functionality within pilot deployments. The document demonstrates how the DATAMITE solution operates in various operational environments, showcasing both the flexibility of its configuration and its ability to adapt to specific requirements – ranging from deployments on cloud platforms to in-house solutions used for security and integration purposes.

The scope of the document includes a detailed description of the **final real-world demonstration strategy**, including the continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) procedures developed within Task 5.1. It also presents the **final results of technical, operational, and security activities** that constitute the basis for demonstrating the system's functionality in the pilots implemented under Task 5.2.

D5.4 serves as the final demonstrator deliverable of WP5, consolidating the outcomes of the second pilot iteration and providing a validated reference baseline for future deployment, exploitation, and replication activities.

1.2 Document Structure

This deliverable is broken down into the following sections:

- **Section 1 Introduction** provides the deliverable's general context, dependencies, and structure.
- **Section 2 Continuous Integration of the DATAMITE Components** presents the integration, including CI/CD tools, procedures and guidelines.
- **Section 3 Pilot Demonstrators** reports on the pilot demonstrators developed within the DATAMITE project. It provides links to each pilot's demo materials including videos and screenshots. This section illustrates how the integrated system performs in real-world settings, showcasing its adaptability and effectiveness in meeting diverse operational requirements.

1.3 Document Dependencies

This document represents the **second and final iteration** of the Pilot Demonstrators deliverable within WP5. It builds upon the intermediate results presented in Deliverable D5.3, which documented the initial deployment and first validation phase of the DATAMITE framework within pilot environments.

D5.4 consolidates the outcomes of the second pilot iteration completed in M35, reflecting the final configuration of the framework, validated use cases, and results of the demonstration and validation campaigns carried out under Tasks T5.2 and T5.4.

The work reported in this deliverable is aligned with the pilot definitions in D1.1, the requirements and architecture described in D1.2, and the data management and protection principles defined in D7.7 and D7.8. Compared to D5.3, this deliverable **does not report** progress but instead provides evidence of completed deployments and validated demonstrators.

2 Continuous Integration of the DATAMITE Components

This section provides an overview of the **continuous integration and deployment practices applied in the DATAMITE project to support the final pilot demonstrators**, as developed under Task 5.1. It describes the CI/CD tools, integration procedures, and guidelines that were **used to ensure reliable, repeatable, and controlled deployments** of the DATAMITE framework across heterogeneous pilot environments. In addition, the section summarises the **framework releases effectively utilised in the final pilot deployments**, ensuring system stability, quality, and traceability.

2.1 CI/CD tools

This subsection outlines the core tools used to implement CI/CD procedures within the DATAMITE project. The **GitLab repository** serves as the central source code management and CI platform for the framework, while **DockerHub** is used for building, storing, and distributing container images deployed in the pilot environments.

GitLab Repository:

<https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project>

DockerHub:

<https://hub.docker.com/search?q=DATAMITE>

These tools were consistently used throughout the project to support automated builds, testing, and deployment of DATAMITE components in the pilot infrastructures.

2.2 CI procedures and integration guidelines

This subsection describes the CI/CD pipelines and the main stages applied when committing changes to the DATAMITE framework. The pipelines implement automated processes for code validation, container image creation, and deployment preparation, ensuring consistency between development and pilot environments.

The CI/CD procedures and integration guidelines are documented and maintained in the project repository and were applied to support the deployment of the final demonstrators:

CI/CD pipelines documentation:

https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project/docs/-/blob/main/ci_cd.md?ref_type=heads

These procedures enabled controlled evolution of the framework while maintaining compatibility with the pilot-specific configurations.

2.3 Releases of the DATAMITE framework

This subsection summarises the **DATAMITE framework releases used to support the final pilot deployments**. The validated release adopted for the demonstrators is based on a **Docker Swarm implementation**, which was successfully deployed across different pilot infrastructures. This approach provides a lightweight and flexible orchestration mechanism suitable for both cloud-based and in-house environments.

In addition to the core framework, supporting components were documented and validated, including:

- the **data-sharing logging tool**,
- the data product composition tool,
- the anonymization tool,
- the user defined rules generator (URDG),
- the Gaia-X dataproduct onboarding ces publishing,
- the data harmonization tools,
- the Eclipse Data Connector policy engine extension,
- the Eclipse Data Connector logging service extension,
- the **brokering service for integration with the AI on Demand (AIoD) Platform**.

The following release and documentation resources were used in the context of the final demonstrators:

Release 1

https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/DATAMITE-project/data-support-tools/data_ingestion_and_storage/infrastructure

Documentations:

DATAMITE's Logging tool:

<https://DATAMITE-logging-tool.readthedocs.io/en/latest/index.html>

DATAMITE's Data Product Composition tool:

<https://data-product-composition.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

DATAMITE's Anonymization tool:

<https://anonymisation-tool.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

DATAMITE's User Defined Rules Generator (UDRG)

<https://datamite-logging-service-extension.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

DATAMITE's brokering service for the AI on Demand Platform:

<https://aiod-broker.readthedocs.io/en/latest/introduction.html>

DATAMITE's Gaia-X dataproduct onboarding ces publishing

<https://datamite-gaia-x-onboarding.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

DATAMITE's Harmonization tools:

ICCS: <https://iccs-data-harmonization.readthedocs.io/en/latest/>

PSNC: <https://psnc-data-harmonization-tools.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

DATAMITE's Eclipse Data Connector Logging Service Extension:

<https://datamite-logging-service-extension.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

DATAMITE's Eclipse Data Connector Policy Engine Extension

<https://datamite-logging-service-extension.readthedocs.io/en/latest>

The CI/CD practices and framework releases described in this section constituted a **stable technical baseline** for the deployment, integration, and validation of all pilot demonstrators presented in Section 3.

3 Pilot Demonstrators

The DATAMITE project infrastructure and software were deployed using a strategic approach tailored to the specific requirements of each pilot. Different configurations were employed to ensure optimal performance and scalability in various environments – for instance, some pilots utilised dedicated virtual machines on cloud platforms such as Azure or Google Cloud, while others relied on in-house solutions to meet specific security or integration needs. This diversified deployment strategy not only supports the seamless integration of key modules but also enables the framework to adapt to various data exchange protocols and operational constraints.

A summary is in the Table 1:

Pilot no.	Pilot name	Infrastructure
Pilot 1	Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with EDIH support	2 VMs (Ubuntu) Private DPC
Pilot 2	Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange	VM (Debian) on-premises
Pilot 3	Offering Data to Service Providers with Data Spaces	VM (Ubuntu) on Google Cloud Platform
Pilot 4	Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data	VM (Windows) and Storage Account in Azure
Pilot 5	Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets	IaaS (OpenStack – bare VMs, various architecture) / PaaS (OpenShift)
Pilot 6	Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AloD Platform	1 VM (Ubuntu) in-house cloud

Table 1: Pilots deployed infrastructure.

In addition to the deployed infrastructure, each pilot offers access to demonstrator instances showcasing the implemented services and workflows. A summary of the demonstrators and their access endpoints is presented in Table 2.

Pilot no.	Demonstrator	Reference
1	Accessing and uploading datasets as FACSA	Demo Video 1
1	Accessing and uploading datasets as OBREMO	Demo Video 2
1	Accessing as FACSA or OBREMO to inspect datasets metadata	Demo Video 3
1	Dataset enrichment and ML	Demo Video 4

Pilot no.	Demonstrator	Reference
2	Creating a dataset and associate it with a domain	Demo1 Demo Video 1
2	Evaluating the quality of a dataset	Demo2 Demo Video 2
2	Enabling queries to be executed across multiple heterogeneous databases (e.g. relational, NoSQL)	Demo 3
3	Definition of <i>Glossary</i> and <i>Terms</i> , bulk uploading of dataset files to the platform, and connection to HEDNO's PostgreSQL database	Demo Video 1
3	Operations and functionalities related to data product composition, anonymisation, and the creation and execution of PostgreSQL queries	Demo Video 2
3	Data quality assessment of the datasets	Demo Video 3
3	Defining an access/usage policy for a data product	Demo Video 4
4	Creating a data product	Demo Video 1
4	Evaluating governance mechanisms	Demo Video 2
4	Evaluating data quality rules	Demo Video 3
4	Sharing data to Open Data Portal	Demo Video 4
5	Creating a domain, glossary and terms	Demo Video 1
5	Creating a dataset in the DATAMITE platform, check its characteristics and create custom rules	Demo Video 2
5	Creating a data product from defined dataset and publishing it on the Pontus-X ecosystem	Demo Video 3
6	A brief overview of the pilot scenarios, test-bed dissemination of MISTRAL data products on EU portals	Demo Video 1
6	A brief overview of quality tagging, test-bed quality assessment of sensor data with ad-hoc rule	Demo Video 2

Table 2: Pilot demonstrators

3.1 Corporate Multi-Domain Data Exchange with EDIH support demonstrator

3.1.1 Final deployment and configuration

In this section, the details corresponding to the final deployment and configuration of the DATAMITE framework adapted to the needs of Pilot 1 are presented.

Regarding the infrastructure, it has been deployed following an “on-premises” philosophy, on a virtual machine set up within the company’s own environment.

The machine specifications are as follows:

- 8 processing cores
- 16 GB of RAM
- 50 GB of storage
- Ubuntu 24.04 LTS operating system

The deployment was carried out using the official repository hosted on GitLab, making use of the tools provided by the Docker suite, including Docker Hub itself.

The authentication and user management system has been integrated into the company’s own Keycloak instance, allowing user provisioning to be carried out using the internal corporate accounts of internal users.

The deployment was carried out including all the components of the framework, but the following are the ones that were ultimately tested through the scenarios planned in this second validation period:

- Data discovery tools
- Data ingestion and storage
- Data governance
- Data product composition
- Quality evaluator
- KPI library
- User-defined rules generators.

No substantial differences were proposed regarding the scenarios developed in the first testing period. Under this premise, the changes focused on the additional integrations carried out with the organization’s internal systems, as well as new versions of the components that have been developed in recent months by the teams responsible for Work Packages 2 and 3.

Thanks to this, tests that were previously incomplete or could not be conducted with the level of quality we would have preferred to have now been fully and successfully carried out.

3.1.2 Final demonstrator and validation outcomes

The designed and deployed demonstrator allows full integration into our data centre infrastructure. As mentioned in the previous section, the internal virtualization system has been used. All environments deployed in our infrastructure follow two different patterns: on the one hand, the

possibility of setting up a specific and dedicated virtual machine for the tool; on the other hand, deployment through containers orchestrated via Docker¹. In this case, this second deployment option has been chosen.

Under this premise, the different modules of the framework have been deployed in a semi-isolated manner within their respective containers, using the appropriate configuration to enable interconnections through virtual ports. This deployment follows the typical pattern of distributed applications, as required and customary for other applications and tools deployed within the group's architecture. With this approach, the goal is to achieve a full integration of the DATAMITE framework with the rest of the third-party systems that form part of the overall architecture.

The demonstration is carried out through testing scenarios specifically designed to simulate normal operational processes. In this sense, the aim is to emulate an integration of the framework into the corporate data architecture, as well as into internal operations.

In this context, two users/agents have been prepared who will work independently, just as two users belonging to the two group companies participating in the project would do: on the one hand, a FACSA² user, and on the other, an OBREMO³ user.

Regarding the roles associated with the project, although both users would be able to perform any of the roles/functions, for the purpose of the test at hand one user will act as the data source, while the other will be the sink or consumer of that data.

In this context, three tests were carried out:

- Contribution and publication of datasets
- Querying and consumption of datasets
- Enrichment and modification of datasets

For each of these tests, the following key aspects were analysed to assess the degree to which the objectives proposed during the design of the DATAMITE framework have been achieved:

- Contribution and publication of datasets
- Evaluation of the dataset upload process through the different drivers provided by the framework
- Dataset-specific glossary
- Indicators and statistics associated with the data
- Querying and consumption of datasets
- Access to the marketplace of published datasets
- Visualization of metadata and summaries of published datasets
- Access to the dataset of interest for the user
- Enrichment and modification of datasets
- Download and modification of a published dataset, including new specific columns

¹ <https://www.docker.com/>

² <https://www.facsa.com/>

³ <https://www.obremo.es/>

- Integration of a dataset derived from the execution of ML models

During the execution of the testing operations, a set of recordings was made that includes the operations carried out. The different user interactions were monitored, just as a specific user from one of the group's companies would do in a real production environment.

Below are the different access URLs to the public repository where these recordings have been included, with the aim of facilitating access to and viewing of them:

- Scenario 1:
 - Accessing and uploading datasets as FACSA --> static.nealis.com/video/PT1.mp4
 - Accessing and uploading datasets as OBREMO --> static.nealis.com/video/PT2.mp4
- Scenario 2:
 - Accessing as FACSA or OBREMO to inspect datasets metadata --> static.nealis.com/video/PT3.mp4
- Scenario 3:
 - Dataset enrichment and ML --> static.nealis.com/video/PT4.mp4

According to the scenarios, following objectives have been achieved in this new period of testing; some of them were pending from previous period:

- Accomplished objectives:
- Integration and incorporation of data:
- Connectors for different databases and sources, specifically for PostgreSQL
- Glossary generation and incorporation
- Datasets KPIs and statistics.
- Data access
- Marketplace and data exploration
- Datasets download
- Security and access control
- Corporation Keycloak integration
- Different users and roles

Despite the practical totality of the objectives have been accomplished and validated, some features in terms of security are simple or not provided. However, this is not critical at this point because we have been able to meet minimum security requirements and are complemented by internal security protocols.

3.2 Corporate Multi-Site Data Exchange demonstrator

3.2.1 Final deployment and configuration

The DATAMITE framework is deployed on OTE on-premises infrastructure (Figure 1), utilizing a high-performance HPE ProLiant DL385 Gen11 server, designed to support large-scale data processing, analytics, and stress-testing activities. The server is equipped with two AMD EPYC 9135 processors and 512 GB of DDR5 memory, providing sufficient computational capacity for both data-intensive and control-plane workloads. In addition, two NVIDIA A16 GPUs with 64 GB of RAM each are installed and dedicated to analytical and acceleration tasks. Storage is configured using a RAID 5 array composed of five HPE 1.92 TB NVMe RI SFF U.3 SSDs for data and container workloads, while the hypervisor operating system is hosted on a separate RAID 1 array using two HPE 960 GB NVMe RI SFF U.3 SSDs.

On top of the bare-metal setup, an enterprise-grade virtualization environment has also been deployed on the same server. This virtualization layer enables the controlled creation of isolated virtual machines and virtualized clusters, allowing the DATAMITE framework to be evaluated under different virtualized deployment scenarios. This setup is used to assess performance characteristics, resource contention effects, and potential performance degradation when the DATAMITE framework operates in virtualized environments, as opposed to direct bare-metal execution. Such testing is particularly relevant for validating portability and robustness across heterogeneous infrastructure configurations commonly encountered in real-world deployments.

From the operating system perspective, the deployment runs on Debian 13 (Trixie)⁴. The system follows an OTE-specific monitoring implementation that enables comprehensive monitoring of hardware resources, system performance, and network interfaces. In addition, dedicated monitoring extensions based on Node Exporter have been deployed to capture energy-consumption metrics at container level, allowing energy-aware analysis of DATAMITE services and workloads.

All DATAMITE framework components are containerized and orchestrated using Docker v29.1.3, with Docker Swarm employed as the orchestration mechanism. The current configuration follows a single-node Swarm deployment, where the same node acts as both manager and worker. This setup ensures operational simplicity, while remaining compatible with future horizontal scaling and multi-node extensions.

For data persistence and evaluation purposes, the deployment integrates a heterogeneous database stack consisting of MongoDB v8 (exposed on port 27027), MariaDB v12.1 (exposed on port 27028), and PostgreSQL v18.1 (exposed on port 27029). Due to substantial changes introduced in PostgreSQL 18.x, several encryption-related configurations were adapted during deployment. To ensure interoperability with existing components and legacy configurations, PostgreSQL was configured to maintain compatibility with version 17.x, using MD5-based authentication mechanisms where required. Across the deployed databases, more than 200

⁴ <https://www.debian.org/releases/trixie/>

million entries were loaded and tested, covering functional validation, performance benchmarking, and durability under stress conditions.

In collaboration with associated research institutes (ICCS and CERTH), large-scale synthetic datasets were deployed outside the perimeter of the OTE internal network. This architectural choice enables realistic stress testing of the DATAMITE framework, including throughput, latency, and resilience evaluations, without affecting operational OTE services.

Communication between the OTE on-premises deployment and the external database infrastructure is supported either through a dedicated VPN channel or via direct public IP connectivity, both of which are currently used in parallel testing scenarios. This dual-mode connectivity allows the evaluation of the framework under secure controlled conditions as well as under real-world network exposure.

Overall, this deployment configuration ensures that DATAMITE is assessed on production-grade hardware, under realistic network conditions and large-scale data volumes, while also validating its behaviour in virtualized environments, providing strong evidence of its performance, scalability, and operational maturity.

Figure 1: Pilot 2 infrastructure

3.2.2 Final demonstrator and validation outcomes

In Pilot 2, DATAMITE framework has been validated against 3 demo scenarios:

Demo 1: Create a dataset and associate it with a domain

As mentioned in deliverable D5.1 (section 4.2) the main goal of this pilot is to identify inconsistencies across three distinct heterogeneous data repositories within the organization,

exploiting the capabilities of DATAMITE framework. These databases correspond to different operational units, each one managing critical aspects of the organization’s infrastructure and services:

- The **Customer Database (MariaDB)** captures the organization’s view of each customer, focusing on identification, service relationships, and engagement history. It joins individual customers or companies that have business relation with OTE to their subscribed products and overall customer significance.
- The **Infrastructure / Telecom Database (MongoDB)** represents the technical layer of service delivery, detailing the network assets, configurations, and operational parameters associated with each customer’s connection. It reflects the physical (cabinets, routers, fibre optic switches) and logical infrastructure that is in use.
- The **Accounting / Logistics Database (PostgreSQL)** contains the commercial and contractual perspective of the customer relationship, covering apart from billing records, the applied discounts, service packages, and account agreements for each dedicated customer. It ensures that financial and service terms are aligned with the philosophy of the policy that each operating entity has.

To this end, Figure 2 shows the creation of an artifact that represents a snapshot (1000 rows) of OTE’s Customer Data, associated with the telecommunications domain:

Figure 2: Pilot 2 customer dataset

This artifact (CSV file) has been created via the Trino data-support tool of DATAMITE framework, using the query depicted in Figure 3:

OTE_Pilot_Customer_Data ✕

Id	Is Recursive	Name	Timestamp
16	false	OTE_Pilot_Customer_I	2026-01-13T06:58:09.8

Query Result ▼

Query

```
SELECT *
FROM pilot_ote_mariadb.datamite.customers_plain
LIMIT 1000
```

Notes

Execute

Edit

Figure 3: Trino query to create artifact of pilot 2 customer data

It is worth noting that, via Trino, the same query can be used across each of the three databases, regardless of their underlying technology (e.g., relational or NoSQL).

The link to Demo 1 video can be found here: [Pilot 2 Demo Videos](#)

Demo 2: Evaluate the quality of a dataset

Standard quality evaluation (Figure 4) is performed through the KPI library module of DATAMITE framework. Metrics defined by the overall quality dimensions such as completeness or uniqueness are evaluated during the automated profiling, whereas specific requirements of quality are under the scope of other dimensions such as accuracy, timeliness or validity.

Figure 4: Standard quality KPIs of pilot 2 customer data

In addition, the User Defined Rules Generator (UDRG) module allows organizations to define their own rules, based on the knowledge of the sector they belong to, and to perform the required data analysis to ensure that the data quality meets the standards of the organization. Concerning OTE’s Customer Data, there exists a *Timeliness* business quality rule, according to which for the *Customer_Status* to be labelled as “Active”, the corresponding *Started_Date* of the customer’s contract must be within the last 3 years. Given that a customer can be labelled either as “Active”, or “Dormant”, or “Cancelled”, Figure 5 illustrates the definition of the *Timeliness* rule, whereas Figure 6 presents the quality score of the artifact based on that rule.

Figure 5: Definition of timeliness business quality rule regarding pilot 2 customer data

Figure 6: Timeliness quality score of pilot 2 customer data

The link to Demo 2 video can be found here: [Pilot 2 Demo Videos](#)

Demo 3: Enable queries to be executed across multiple heterogeneous databases (e.g. relational, NoSQL)

In OTE, there is a *Consistency* rule, where for each active service in the *Infrastructure / Telecom Database (MongoDB)*, there must be a matching *Accounting / Logistics Database (PostgreSQL)* record with a bill that is generated. This ensures that no service is delivered without proper billing, and no service is offered without being registered to the billing registry. However, an important remark is necessary to be given at this point: the legacy architecture of OTE Group’s logistics system, which is mainly the original design when the system kicked off, is following the business model of that era, meaning to evaluate sales bonuses based on value-added products and not by unified customer profiles or, in general, the number of new customers entering the group. For example, if an existing customer of the group has an OTE TV contract and later they ask to install an OTE Fiber line (even for the same office), then the system would automatically generate a completely new contract ID, since it would be a different service. As a result, a new database entry would have a new primary key for that specific new service. Thus, it would not update the existing customer record, as the design of the database does not follow that approach. Even considering also the scenario where a different customer or even the same would like to buy a service for vacation home(s), which often involves different branches, sales agents, and in many cases regional billing policies (e.g., different VAT rates on some Greek islands). Consequently, those are the reasons why a single unique customer often appears multiple times in the database, with each entry representing a specific product subscription. The data inconsistencies based on the billing *Consistency* rule can be identified via the Trino tool, using the query depicted in Figure 7:

OTE_Pilot_Consistency_Rule
✕

Id	Is Recursive	Name	Timestamp
22	false	OTE_Pilot_Consistency_Rt	2026-01-18T12:14:51.505Z

Query Result ▼

Query

```
SELECT DISTINCT t.customer_id
FROM pilot_ote_mongo.mydatabase.telecom t
LEFT JOIN pilot_ote_postgres.public.logistic_database l
ON t.customer_id = l.customer_id
WHERE l.total_bill IS NULL
```

Notes

Result

customer_id
MUDS3593
NDDA7056
NDDA1214
OKKS2789
MUDS2673

Execute
Edit

Figure 7: Trino query to identify data inconsistencies based on the billing consistency rule

To highlight the actual goal, which is to satisfy the *Consistency* rule, the `DISTINCT` clause was added into the query logic. This extra addition allows firstly to aggregate these records and identify unique users, thus presenting a clean baseline before drilling into the specific details of each account.

3.3 Offering Data to Service Providers with Data Spaces demonstrator

3.3.1 Final deployment and configuration

In the first iteration of the demonstration, HEDNO presented the following processes:

- Definition of glossary and terms
- Bulk upload of dataset files to the platform
- Connection to HEDNO's PostgreSQL database
- Creation of a data product from multiple datasets
- Bundling of a composite data product
- Creation of a sensitive list for anonymisation
- Anonymisation using various techniques
- Creation and execution of PostgreSQL queries

The above processes are included in [Demo Video 1](#) (processes 1–3) and [Demo Video 2](#) (processes 4–8), which were presented in Deliverable D5.3. However, in those videos, several features were not sufficiently mature, mainly with respect to the final UI. In the following sections, we present screenshots and detailed descriptions of the improvements that have been implemented and are related to the processes of Iteration 1. Furthermore, we focus on the demonstration and validation of data quality assessment processes using user-defined rules, and the definition of access and usage policies applied to data products before publishing using the EDC connector, both presented with two additional detailed videos.

Although the initial objective of this deliverable was, in addition to data quality, to include a full demonstration of the framework's capabilities for data sharing through an Energy Data Space, and specifically through *Data Cellar*⁵, this was ultimately not possible, as these capabilities are not yet fully integrated into the DATAMITE framework. Nevertheless, these processes are at the core of Pilot 3 and will be included in Deliverable D5.2 at M39.

For the execution of the demonstration, a virtual machine leased by HEDNO was used, running Ubuntu Server 24.04, on which the DATAMITE components were deployed. From our side, we conducted extensive testing of the deployed components, in close collaboration with the component developers and the pipeline integrator. We reported numerous technical issues and contributed to their rapid resolution, as well as to the overall enhancement of the platform's capabilities and functionalities.

3.3.2 Final demonstrator and validation outcomes

In Iteration 1, the capabilities of the Access Control mechanism, based on the Keycloak framework were limited, as UI-level integration had not been fully implemented. In Iteration 2, the Access Control functionality has been fully integrated. In Figure 8, we demonstrate the new user

⁵ <https://datacellarproject.eu/>

registration page and the required information. We can also observe that DATAMITE now supports access via SSL.

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `auth.hedno.datamite-horizon.eu/realms/datamite/login-actions/registration?client_id=datamite.user.interface&tab_id=DE4ZjhLej0E&client_data=eyJydSI6Im...`. The page is titled "User registration page" and features a dark blue background with a white grid pattern. The registration form includes the following fields and values:

- Username: kkontodimas
- Password: (masked with dots)
- Confirm password: (masked with dots)
- Email: k.kontodimas@dieddie.gr
- First name: Konstantinos
- Last name: Kontodimas

At the bottom of the form, there is a link for "Back to Login" and a prominent "Register" button.

Figure 8: User registration page.

3.3.2.1 Updates on Glossary and Terms Definition

The demonstration presented in [Demo Video 1](#) of Iteration 1 included the definition of *Glossary* and *Terms*, bulk uploading of dataset files to the platform, and connection to HEDNO's PostgreSQL database. With respect to these functionalities, no major changes have been introduced, apart from improvements to the platform's UI. However, it is now possible to associate Glossary Terms with Artifact columns, which allows easy identification of columns, viewing detailed column descriptions, and identifying relationships between columns from within the same, or from across different datasets. The association of columns to Terms is demonstrated in Figure 9.

TRANSFORMER Columns

Creation date	Last Edition	Keywords	Data type
Jan 19 2026, 02:17:20	Jan 19 2026, 02:17:20		String

Full description

Short description

Column KPIs Lineage Domains **Glossary**

Associate Term 4 Term(s) associated Search Filters Sort by Last updated

Name	Description
Substation term	A facility for voltage transformation and power distribution.
Medium Voltage term	Voltage between low and high voltage, used for distribution.
Client transformer term	Transformer identification number.
Transformer term	A device that changes voltage levels in AC systems.

Figure 9: Association of the TRANSFORMER column from metering data to relevant Terms.

3.3.2.2 Updates on Data Product Composition

In [Demo Video 2](#) of Iteration 1, we demonstrated operations and functionalities related to data product composition, anonymisation, and the creation and execution of PostgreSQL queries.

The first part of the operations related to data product composition validated:

- The creation of a data product from multiple artifacts, and
- The bundling of a composite data product consisting of different artifact types retrieved from different datasets

In the first case, we created a unified data product from metering data of HEDNO's Telemetry Centre, after removing columns containing sensitive information, and aggregated them into a single artifact.

In the second case, we bundled a) power, voltage, and load measurements from the SCADA system of a HEDNO substation for the year 2022, b) a metering data artifact from the Telemetry Centre for the year 2022, and c) a PowerFactory file containing the medium-voltage line model of the network related to the above measurements

Within this context, the Data Product Composition functionality was already available in Iteration 1. In Iteration 2, it has been fully integrated with the rest of the DATAMITE framework. Below, we

present screenshots from the new UI highlighting this integration (Figure 10, Figure 11, Figure 12).

Figure 10: Filling data product metadata.

Figure 11: Selection of Artifacts to be used in the data product creation.

Figure 12: Selecting actions to be performed for data transformation.

3.3.2.3 Updates on Anonymisation

In the second part, related to anonymisation, we tested all anonymisation techniques available during Iteration 1 on metering data from the Telemetry Centre, in order to hide the supply number of medium-voltage substations, which had been previously included in a Sensitive List, as it constitutes sensitive information. However, in Iteration 1 we performed the demonstration using the Swagger interface of Data Anonymisation Tool's API. In Iteration 2, the *Anonymization Tool* has been fully integrated into the DATAMITE framework, adopting a new UI. In Figure 13 we present the UI, at the step of selecting an anonymisation technique.

Figure 13: User registration page.

3.3.2.4 Updates on creation and execution of PostgreSQL queries

In the final part, concerning the creation and execution of PostgreSQL queries, during Iteration 1 we created and executed:

- A query for extracting metering data from the Telemetry Centre database
- Queries for extracting power, voltage, and load measurements from the SCADA PostgreSQL database

In Iteration 2, query creation and execution have been fully integrated into the unified DATAMITE environment, using a single, consistent UI. The following images demonstrate this functionality.

Figure 14: Query creation using Trino through the DATAMITE UI.

Figure 15: Query execution using Trino through the DATAMITE UI.

3.3.2.5 Data Quality Assessment Using User-Defined Rules

For the data quality assessment of the datasets, we created [Demo Video 3](#), in which we present in detail the creation of new quality rules for SCADA power measurements. Specifically, we demonstrate the addition of four user-defined quality rules addressing:

- Evaluation of the temporal consistency between the actual measurement timestamps and the timestamps recorded by the SCADA system
- Evaluation of the completeness of critical dataset columns
- Evaluation of record consistency between the recorded power type (active or reactive) and the corresponding unit of measurement (MW or MVar)
- Evaluation of record validity with respect to power type and unit of measurement

Correspondingly, we also demonstrate quality rules for the remaining datasets (SCADA load and voltage measurements from 2022, and metering data from the Telemetry Centre). For all datasets, we present built-in basic metrics at column level, dataset-level KPIs, scores of the user-defined quality rules, and the built-in KPIs for selected dataset columns.

3.3.2.6 Definition of Access / Usage Policies

To demonstrate the process of defining an access/usage policy for a data product, [Demo Video 4](#) was recorded. It shows the sequence of steps that are followed to define a policy for a data product that contains various measurements using the EDC Connector. The process involves:

- filling in the publication's details containing a name and a description and
- adding policy rules in the policies by selecting a rule type, action and setting constraints.

Using the Policy Orchestration Tool, a policy can be defined by selecting a category, an action to be performed as well as constraints regarding that action, such as time intervals. Finally, after the policy has been created the publication's metadata are reviewed by the HEDNO user, the data product is able to be published to a data space. However, the data products are not actually published to a data space, since we haven't used valid participant credentials for an existing data space.

In the demonstration video, we show three publication examples of different data products, using various policy rules.

3.3.2.7 Further Extensions

In Iteration 2, we expected to conclude the validation plan in Deliverable D5.4, including data product exchange through Energy Dataspaces. Since integration with Data Cellar has not yet been completed within DATAMITE, we expect to perform onboarding to Data Cellar and data product exchange with CERTH in Deliverable D5.2 at M39.

3.4 Leveraging Electricity Distribution Open Data demonstrator

3.4.1 Final deployment and configuration

During this reporting period, E-REDES completed the second phase of Pilot 4, focusing on the utilization of the DATAMITE framework for dataset sharing, integration, and validation within the system. The testing activities began with Level 2 validations, which involved executing a series of functional tasks such as creating data products, defining custom data quality rules, establishing glossaries and terms, and analysing KPIs. Subsequently, Level 3 validations were carried out to assess data transfer workflows from the SFTP environment to the Open Data Portal.

For testing purposes, an ITI-provided virtual machine (VM) was employed, as the E-REDES VM experienced periods of unavailability, compounded by certain DATAMITE framework issues. Following the release of the framework second version, the original Windows-based VM was no longer compatible; therefore, an Ubuntu-based VM was requested to ensure system operability.

The DATAMITE framework was deployed in this environment using Docker, sourced from GitHub and configured under the guidance of the project's technical partners.

The components tested during this iteration of the deliverable included:

- Data ingestion and storage
- Data governance
- Data quality evaluator
- Metadata repository
- Data product composition

3.4.2 Final demonstrator and validation outcomes

For pilot 4 a series of demonstration demos was produced, showcasing how to perform several tasks through the platform that are a part of level 2 and level 3 validations. A demo illustrating the interaction with the Open Data portal was also made. Although with some limitations, related to the FTP connector type, it enables the demonstration of how the different components should interact in a production ready solution. All these demonstrations were a result of the second phase.

Demo 1 - [Creating a Data Product](#)

This video demonstrated the process of creating a data product using a CSV file as an example.

The procedure began by creating a new dataset:

- Click the “New Dataset” button.
- Complete the required fields with basic information such as the dataset's name and description.
- Optionally, associate the dataset with relevant domains or glossary terms to improve classification and discoverability within the framework.

Next, the user selected the data ingestion method. The available options included batch, streaming, database connection, and database query. For this demonstration, the batch/bulk upload method was used:

- Upload the file.
- Define the file's name and type.

Once the final confirmation was given, the dataset was created, containing the uploaded artifact (CSV file) within it.

The next step was to create a data product based on the newly uploaded artifact:

- Navigate to the “Data Products” tab.
- Click the “Create Data Product” button.
- Provide the name and description for the data product.
- Select the artifact just uploaded, with the option to combine it with other artifacts.
- Configure the artifact by retaining, deleting, or filtering specific columns as needed.

After completing these steps, the process of creating the data product was finalised, and the product became available within the framework (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Data product created

Demo 2 and 3 - Evaluating [governance mechanisms](#) and [data quality rules](#)

For this demonstration, two scenarios were presented. The first showcased the governance mechanisms, specifically the ability to create domains, glossaries, and terms. Each dataset could be associated with one or more domains, and each domain could belong to multiple datasets, making it easier to identify datasets with similar thematic classifications. Glossaries could be created to store terms, which could also be assigned to different datasets. Furthermore, terms

within a glossary could maintain semantic relationships such as synonyms and antonyms, enhancing metadata consistency and discoverability.

The second scenario focused on data quality rules, covering both the default quality checks included in the framework and the creation of custom quality rules. This part of the demonstration showed how datasets could be evaluated against the established rules and how the results could be interpreted.

Governance mechanisms creation process:

- Domain creation: Access the Govern tab, navigate to the Domain section, and provide the necessary information — name and description.
- Glossary creation: Access the Governance tab, select Glossary, click New Glossary, and complete the required fields including name, description, language of terms, usage, and the associated domain (if applicable). Once confirmed, the glossary was created.
- Adding terms: Within the created glossary, click Add Term, provide the name, description, abbreviation, and usage, and optionally define synonym or antonym relations with other terms. After confirmation, the term was successfully added to the glossary.

Data quality rules (when accessing an artifact, the demonstration highlighted the default checks implemented in the framework):

- Duplicate detection - to identify repeated records in the dataset.
- Null value detection - to identify missing data in fields.

These checks are useful for detecting early-stage issues or inconsistencies. However, during the recording, a display issue prevented these values from being shown (see Figure 17). This limitation was reported to the technical partners responsible for the component and is expected to be resolved.

Figure 17: Pre-defined quality rules with no values

The framework enabled the creation of custom quality rules, and the demonstration illustrated this process step by step. Within an artifact, a dedicated “Quality Rules” tab was available, from which the option “Add Quality Rule” could be selected. After specifying the title and description of the quality rule, relevant dimensions could be assigned to define the aspects the rule would evaluate.

In the subsequent configuration window, the rule’s elements were defined. Multiple elements could be included within the same rule, and each could be enabled or disabled at the time of creation. The demonstration showcased several possible configurations using the previously uploaded artifact as an example.

Once the process was completed, the newly created custom rule appeared in the framework, along with its score and associated details (see Figure 18). However, certain inconsistencies were identified: although the rule was successfully created, the system did not provide complete feedback regarding its results (e.g. detailed percentages or evaluation metrics).

Discussions with the technical partners were initiated to address this limitation. The final demonstrator reflects the implemented and validated functionalities available at the time of demonstration.

Figure 18: Custom quality rules with no score

Demo 4 - [Sharing data to Open Data portal](#)

This video demonstrated the process through which data, once uploaded to the framework, could be transferred to an external storage location - in this case, an SFTP server - and subsequently integrated into E-REDES Open Data portal⁶.

The first step involved creating a publication, assuming a pre-existing data product. The procedure for creating such a data product had already been presented in [Demo 1](#).

Upon selecting “Create Publication”, the interface displayed the data product intended for publication to the SFTP server. For this demonstration, our data product was selected along with the Opendatasoft portal as a target destination.

To transfer data to the SFTP server, it was necessary to provide a publication token with a specific structure containing the SFTP credentials: username, password, host, port, and the directory path where the data would be stored.

In addition to defining the name and description of the publication, the process also supported the inclusion of column-level metadata, such as column descriptions, labels, and names. Further options allowed modification of the file name, assignment of keywords, specification of dataset themes, dataset URLs, version numbers, and other relevant attributes.

Once these steps were completed, the publication was created within the framework. Upon accessing the corresponding SFTP location, three files could be observed (see Figure 19):

- A schema file representing the artifact’s structure;

⁶ [Portal - Homepage — E-REDES](#)

- A data file containing the actual dataset;
- An index file including metadata related to all files published to the SFTP.

However, the final stage - transferring data from the SFTP server to the Open Data Portal - could not be demonstrated due to two main constraints:

- Testing access to the broker was granted only shortly before the deliverable deadline, leaving insufficient time to explore this functionality in depth.
- During connection tests, it was identified that the Open Data Portal only supported FTP connections, while our tests were conducted using SFTP. This will require a modification of the broker to enable FTP connectivity in addition to SFTP.

Due to these limitations, the data transfer between FTP and Open Data Portal was only tested manually. We can see in Figure 20 the Opendatasoft harvester that went through the metadata file generated in the SFTP and got the information that a new file existed named “Dataset27 dp – artifact 1”. Then, in Figure 21 and Figure 22, that new file was ingested into the Open Data portal successfully and was available in the platform. Finally, in Figure 23, we can verify that the metadata was successfully loaded into the Open Data portal.

Name	Size	Changed	Rights	Owner
schema_27_Sobretsenoes_a_opendatasoft_version_1.csv	1 KB	12/01/2026 12:51:01	nwxr-xr-x	root
index.csv	1 KB	12/01/2026 12:51:01	nw-rw-r--	23505
27_Sobretsenoes_a_opendatasoft_version_1.csv	523 KB	12/01/2026 12:51:01	nw-rw-r--	23505

Figure 19: Files published to SFTP

Figure 20: Opendatasoft analysing index metadata

Figure 21: Opendatasoft ingesting file mentioned in index metadata

Figure 22: File ingested in opendatasoft

Field	Identifier	Type	Description
1. year	year	Text	—
2. quarter	quarter	Text	—
3. code	code	Text	—
4. name	name	Text	—
5. tension	tension	Decimal	—
6. startdate	startdate	Datetime	—
7. enddate	enddate	Datetime	—
8. county	county	Text	—
9. district	district	Text	—

Figure 23: Metadata from file ingested into opendatasoft

Sharing data to an Energy Data Space

Unfortunately, it was not possible to present a demonstration of data sharing with the Energy Data Space, as this process required a functioning connection to the Data Cellar data space. An attempt was initially made to carry out the onboarding independently; however, a roadblock was encountered midway. Following this, the technical partners were contacted, and they took the initiative to liaise with the responsible team at Data Cellar. Despite these efforts, only minimal updates were received, and no operational progress was made in time for this deliverable.

In summary, the second phase of Pilot 4 enabled the successful validation of several key framework components - including data ingestion and storage, governance mechanisms, metadata management, and data product composition - through Level 2 and Level 3 testing activities. Demonstrations showcased the end-to-end creation of datasets and data products, the definition of custom governance structures and glossary terms, and the evaluation of data quality rules, as well as the configuration of data transfers to the SFTP server for subsequent integration into the Open Data Portal. Nevertheless, certain components could only be partially tested as foreseen for this stage, due largely to infrastructure changes, limited framework availability, and technical issues encountered close to the delivery date. These included column-related errors during data product creation, incomplete feedback and inconsistencies in data quality rule outputs, restrictions in broker access and delays in its configuration, SFTP-to-FTP compatibility gaps affecting the Open Data Portal integration, and the postponement of the Data Cellar onboarding process.

Going forward, we will continue working closely with the technical partners to improve these features and ensure they become fully operational. The focus for now will be establishing the connection between FTP and the Open Data Portal, as well as enabling the connection to the Energy Data Space through the Data Cellar. Completing these activities will allow us to run

comprehensive tests and confirm that the end-to-end data flow between the framework and the data consumers is functioning as intended.

3.5 Connecting eDWIN to Data Markets demonstrator

3.5.1 Final deployment and configuration

Deployment configuration

The pilot 5 final deployment reuses servers created for the first iteration of integration with the platform. The whole framework consists of:

- VM hosted in one of the PSNC's Data Centre. Machine is running ubuntu-22.04 OS, 32GB RAM, 8 VCPUs and 100GB SSD. On this machine the DATAMITE framework is deployed, along various APIs used within the project (eDWIN's⁷ meteo service aligned with AIM, Pontus-X API). DATAMITE framework is available at <https://dev.datamite.psnk.pl/>,
- Pontus-X⁸ instance – “Polish Agriculture Data Space” - is deployed in the PaaS framework hosted in PSNC's Data Centre. This portal is part of Pontus-X dev and test networks. Pontus-X instance is available at <https://dataspaces.psnk.pl/>,
- eDWIN and AGREGO subsystems, providing data sets for the pilot. Data sets are first harmonized and then ingested into DATAMITE framework.

The schema representing the pilot's ecosystem and data flow is presented in Figure 24.

⁷ eDWIN (<https://www.edwin.gov.pl/>) farm management system (FMS), which provides few datasets for Pilot 5.

⁸ Pontus-X (<https://www.pontus-x.eu/>) - Open-Source Framework for Value Creation in the Industrial AI & Data Economy, powered by Gaia-X

Figure 24: Pilot 5 high level architecture.

DATAMITE Components

The DATAMITE platform deployed on the machine consists of all available components of the platform, with following being the most important for the pilot 5's use case:

- *DATAMITE portal,*
- *Data Discovery Module,*
- *Data Governance Module:*
 - *Data Catalogue,*
 - *Data Dictionary,*
 - *Data Glossary,*
- *Data Support Tools:*
 - *Data Harmonisation,*
- *Data Sharing Module:*
 - *Data Product Composition,*
 - *Brokers & plugins for other targets [Pontus-X],*
- *Data Quality Module:*
 - *User Defined Rules Generator,*
 - *KPI Library,*
 - *Quality Evaluator.*

Differences from previous iteration

Newest version of DATAMITE platform have been deployed and required configuration of additional DNS sub-domains for Keycloak and MinIO services to run and utilize SSL security. Moreover, development of the Brokers plugin architecture resulted in creation and deployment of Pontus-X API on the pilot's infrastructure to facilitate connecting Pontus-X with DATAMITE platform.

3.5.2 Final demonstrator and validation outcomes

The main goal of pilot 5 is to utilise DATAMITE to integrate datasets produced by two farm and agrifood production management systems – eDWIN and AGREGO - and perform quality evaluation and improvements of their data. Prepared datasets are then transformed into data products and published on the data spaces ecosystem, most notably on Pontus-X data space marketplace. Demonstrators showcased here are focused on presenting outcomes of this integration process.

The final list of datasets chosen to be integrated in the pilot is presented in Table 3.

Data Set	System	Iteration	Mechanism
Meteorological Data	eDWIN	1	REST API Endpoint
Pest Data	eDWIN	1	DB connection + harmonization pipeline
Production Data	AGREGO	1	DB connection + harmonization pipeline
Fertilizers market data	eDWIN	2	REST API Endpoint + harmonization pipeline
Plant Protection Products stats	eDWIN	2	REST API Endpoint + harmonization pipeline
Animal Production Data	AGREGO	2	DB connection + harmonization pipeline

Table 3: Datasets chosen to be integrated in pilot 5

Demonstration 1

The first demonstration covers utilising DATAMITE platform to create a domain, glossary and terms. In our example we will create a plant protection domain (see Figure 25), which covers information about fertilizers and plant protection products (ppp), alongside glossary and two example terms.

Link to the video – Demo 1: <https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/3de01f9d7c204b57a835/>

Create New Domain

1 Domain info

Define a new domain to organize and categorize your datasets more effectively. Provide a clear and concise name and description to ensure proper identification and usage.

1. Domain name

Plant_protection

2. Fill in with the Basic Info

Full description

Plant protection domain

Create

Figure 25: Creating a new domain for plant protection.

In a similar manner all other domains, glossaries and terms relevant to the Pilot 5 use case have been defined and registered in the platform. As an example, a weather glossary is presented in Figure 26, and contains terms representing measurable weather phenomena, such as air temperature, air pressure, relative humidity, wind direction and speed.

Name	Description
<input type="checkbox"/> Wind speed term	Wind speed
<input type="checkbox"/> Wind direction term	Wind direction
<input type="checkbox"/> Precipitation term	Precipitation
<input type="checkbox"/> Humidity term	Humidity
<input type="checkbox"/> Pressure term	Pressure
<input type="checkbox"/> Temperature term	Temperature

Figure 26: A weather glossary for Pilot 5.

From the governance view the user can see what datasets and artifacts have been associated to the specific term to have an overall view of all his data across multiple datasets. This functionality is presented in Figure 27, showcasing that 3 datasets and 1 artifact currently is associated with term Wind Speed.

The screenshot shows the DATAMITE platform interface. The top navigation bar includes 'Dashboard', 'Catalogue', 'Faqs & Documentation', 'Govern', and 'Fairness'. The user profile 'szymon mueller' is visible in the top right. The main content area is titled 'Related Entities' and shows '4 entities related to this term'. The entities listed are:

Name	Type
PME Weather data	dataset
meteo.maxWind	dataset
part2020v2	artifact
meteo.minWind	dataset

Figure 27: Entities associated with term Wind Speed.

Demonstration 2

In the second demonstration we will proceed to create a dataset in the DATAMITE platform, check its characteristics and create custom rules. The demonstration will be divided into a couple of smaller videos.

In the first one we create a new dataset within the DATAMITE platform and upload a csv file containing an aggregated data collected by weather stations integrated within eDWIN project, with over 22,000 entries. We specify that this dataset is part of a Weather data domain and connect it to all defined terms in the Weather glossary. After upload the artifact is available in the Catalogue to be inspected (see Figure 28, which displays aggregated weather data).

Link to video – Demo 2: <https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/1654e1f8822047109c92/>

Figure 28: Displaying the artifact of a weather dataset.

After the dataset is successfully created, we can inspect it to make sure the links to domain and the terms is correct. When inspecting the uploaded artifact, we can see the list of the columns with initial KPIs calculated. Note that it is a collection of data from various types of weather stations – some stations only provide precipitation data (rain stations), some lack precipitation sensors but provide different set of observable phenomena. That’s why some null values are expected in the whole dataset. We can inspect more detailed information and KPIs of each individual column of the artifact, as can be seen in Figure 29 for an *airTemperatureAvg* column of the weather data artifact.

Figure 29: KPI of an individual column of the artifact.

Second part of the demonstration will showcase definition of the custom user defined rules on the artifact we just created. We will create a single rule that will check if max temperature values are lower or equal $+60^{\circ}\text{C}$ and min temperature values are greater or equal -30° (see Figure 30). After applying the rule, we can see the percentage of the values that fulfil the defined rule and compare it to the number of the non-null values.

Link to the video – Demo 3: <https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/36f926839a3e4bd3af1d/>

Include rule as part of the profiling process. Enabled

01 **AND**

1st Operand: airTemperatureMax / Column Value
Operator: <= Less than or equal to
2nd Operand: "60.0"^^xsd:double

02 **+**

1st Operand: airTemperatureMin / Column Value
Operator: >= Greater than or equal to
2nd Operand: "-30.0"^^xsd:double

Define the thresholds and weights for the quality rule to ensure accurate evaluation of your datasets. ⓘ

Add Threshold

Confirm and Create Quality Rule Back

Figure 30: Rules definition of the air temperature.

Demonstration 3

The third demonstrator of the Pilot 5 showcases creating a data product from a defined dataset and publishing it on the Pontus-X ecosystem.

Link to the video – Demo 4: <https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/fb728c2eee99462fa83f/>

The first step is to create a data product from the weather dataset from the previous demonstration. The Data Product Composition wizard allows the user to adjust his data before creating an object that will be published on the data space. For example, some of the columns could be omitted, or aggregation of multiple datasets could be performed (see Figure 31, which represents options available for the aggregated weather data). In the demonstration, we will just create a data product from the dataset as-is.

Figure 31: Creating a weather data product in the Data Product Composition tool.

Once the data product has been created we can proceed to the publication section of the DATAMITE platform. Here we can specify a data product we want to publish and target data space – in our case we specify the Pontus-X ecosystem.

Link to the video – Demo 5: <https://box.pionier.net.pl/f/a0a2e34f3712472c86e4/>

In the following wizard, which maps specific data space schema to DATAMITE metainformation, we can specify details about our publication. In the case of Pontus-X, as a data owner, we must provide a key to our wallet, which will connect it to the asset we are publishing. Other required information are: name of the asset, Pontus-x network to use, url to the asset, asset provider uri, licence and pricing of the asset. In our case we create a free asset. Screenshot of the interaction with the wizard is presented in Figure 32.

Figure 32: Wizard providing Pontus-X specific information required for publication of the asset.

Once the required information is provided the publication of the asset starts. Process takes a while, while necessary operations are taking place in the service responsible for contacting the Pontus-X network; NFTs are created, entries in the blockchain are added etc. Finally, when the process completes, the asset is available to be accessed on the Pontus-X network that we specified, as can be seen in Figure 33.

eDWIN Weather data from Datamite

Pontus-X Testnet

Owned by **Poznan Supercomputing and Networking Center (PSNC)**
 Accessed with SYMBOL

DOWNLOAD | DATASET | Published 25 minutes ago by 0x8e93...848d

eDWIN Weather data from DATAMITE

PSNC | Weather

DATA AUTHOR	OWNER	DID
PSNC	0x8e93...848D	d1d:op:1bed51af080becb12aa34006950c0f1c26796d83b10c344381d2d94d43659b8f

METADATA HISTORY

- published 25 minutes ago ↗

[PREPARE SERVICE CREDENTIAL](#)

Free

Binary 2.15 MB url

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This dataset is free to use. Please note that network gas fees still apply, even when using free assets.

I agree to the Portal Terms and Conditions ↗

I acknowledge that the asset is made available under the MIT license and agree to the terms

Access allowed

No sales yet

Related Assets

Figure 33: Data product published from DATAMITE platform is available in Pontus-X marketplace.

3.6 Connecting MISTRAL to the EU AloD Platform demonstrator

3.6.1 Final deployment and configuration

Final Infrastructure:

The DATAMITE framework is deployed on a virtual machine (VM) within the in-house ADA cloud at CINECA. The VM runs on Ubuntu v24.04 (Noble Edition). The framework containers and related services are orchestrated using Docker v29.1.3. To this end, Docker Swarm was used. The Swarm module is a native container orchestration tool that allows you to manage multiple Docker hosts as a single cluster and uses a manager–worker architecture: managers control the swarm, and workers run containers. The current setup includes a single node acting as both manager and worker node (Figure 34), with 16 CPUs and 120 GB of memory.

Figure 34: Deployment configuration: The green square shows the VM and highlights the swarm node configuration.

DATAMITE Components:

The DATAMITE framework is deployed using the infrastructure repository maintained by ITI in Valencia⁹, which integrates stable versions of all DATAMITE components. The project provides Docker compose files and in-house-written Bash scripts to easily create Swarm nodes and deploy associated services. The full deployment consists of around 32 services, which are based on approximately 60 images.

In the context of the pilot, the following components were tested:

Data discovery tools, Data ingestion and storage, Data governance, Data product composition, EU portal brokers, Quality evaluator, KPI library & User-defined rules generators.

⁹ (https://gitlab.eclipse.org/eclipse-research-labs/datamite-project/data-support-tools/data_ingestion_and_storage/infrastructure.git)

Differences compared to D5.3:

During the previous validation stage, only the components of data support module and data product components were locally deployed and tested, as the other components were still under development.

3.6.2 Final demonstrator and validation outcomes

Description of the demonstrators:

In the pilot, DATAMITE has been used to make MISTRAL¹⁰ platform open datasets available and to check the quality of sensor data. These two elements together comprise two test scenarios of the framework (see Figure 35). MISTRAL (currently named MeteoHub) is an online platform operated by the Italian Meteorological Agency that centralizes national meteorological data, including real-time observations, model forecasts and downloadable datasets. It is managed with support from CINECA. The platform centralizes and standardizes weather data from regional networks across Italy, offering access to a vast data pool that includes real-time inputs from over 4,000 weather stations, millions of daily observations, and numerous forecast and radar datasets. It features advanced map-based visualization with layered weather metrics, and much of the data is freely available as open data for users to download and customize.

Figure 35: Pilot test scenarios

Managing meteorological data involves several significant challenges. These include ensuring high data quality, managing large data volumes, maintaining consistent spatial and temporal resolution, and integrating information from multiple sources. Additional difficulties arise with data sharing, long-term storage, processing, and adherence to privacy and ethical standards. Challenges related to data sharing and quality assurance can restrict the commercial value of meteorological data, limiting opportunities for business growth and innovation.

Validation activities performed:

Validation 1: Sharing open meteorological data through European portals is essential for improving cross-border collaboration, supporting climate research, and strengthening early warning systems for extreme weather events. Open access enables governments, researchers

¹⁰ <https://meteoHub.agenziaitaliameteo.it/ui/homepage?lang=en>

and businesses to reuse consistent, high-quality data, thereby fostering innovation in areas such as climate services, agriculture, energy and disaster risk management. European data portals promote transparency and interoperability, thereby maximizing the societal and economic value of meteorological data, and supporting evidence-based policymaking and climate resilience across Europe. For many businesses, especially start-ups and SMEs, timely, accessible, high-quality data is critical for developing analytics-driven products and services. In this context, the first validation scenario involves publishing MISTRAL datasets on European portals using built-in broker plug-ins (Figure 36).

Figure 36: Validation scenario 1

In short, the process of publishing data is streamlined by uploading MISTRAL metadata into a DATAMITE framework instance via the Data Support Module. This module facilitates the creation of new datasets and the addition of artefacts, i.e. data files. The corresponding metadata is then communicated to the governance module. The data composition module is then used to generate related data products by selecting a dataset and its associated artefacts. These data products are published to European portals, particularly the AIoD and CKAN instances, via broker plug-ins that are seamlessly integrated within the framework.

Validation 2: Assessing the quality of sensor data is crucial to ensure that the information used for analysis and decision-making is accurate, reliable, and fit for purpose. High-quality sensor data minimizes errors, enhances model and forecast performance, and fosters trust among users and stakeholders. Ultimately, robust data quality practices enhance the value of sensor data, enabling more effective scientific, operational and commercial applications. However, observation data often has quality and reliability issues, including missing data, incorrect readings due to sensor failure or calibration issues, and inconsistencies in data units and formats from different sources. For the purpose of this evaluation, testing of the DATAMITE quality module has been carried out for the purpose of the assessment of sensor data errors (Figure 37).

Figure 37: Validation scenario 2

To test the functionality of the quality evaluator, temperature measurements from sensors were used as input. In short, a dataset consisting of both correct and incorrect measurements was created and uploaded to the DATAMITE framework using the data support module. The Quality Evaluator provides statistical metrics derived from the datasets to help identify missing data, duplicates, and value counts. Additionally, ad hoc rules were defined to test the reliability of the sensor data and detect anomalies in temperature measurements. The framework also enables quality KPIs to be downloaded to attach quality tags to the sensors. This improves confidence in using data for downstream applications.

Demonstration videos:

The following link contains videos showing demonstrations of the two scenarios elaborated above.

https://gitlab.hpc.cineca.it/bchandr1/datamite/-/tree/main/DEMO_D5.4

The provision of a brief explanation of the scenario's context is followed by a demonstration of validation using different modules of the framework in both videos.

Achieved Objectives

DATAMITE has been tested to achieve two key objectives: effectively disseminating climate data to European portals and systematically assessing observational data quality. By enabling standardized data publication, DATAMITE improves the visibility, accessibility, and interoperability of climate datasets. This makes the data easily discoverable, accessible and reusable by a wide range of stakeholders, including researchers, public authorities and service providers, while also supporting compliance with European data-sharing frameworks and open data policies.

At the same time, DATAMITE strengthens the quality assessment of observational data by facilitating the extraction of quality KPIs with ad-hoc user defined rules. This helps to understand the accuracy, reliability, and long-term usability of the data, thereby increasing user confidence for utilization in subsequent applications. These improvements together create a more robust and reliable climate data supply chain, enhancing scientific research and supporting evidence-based

decision-making, while generating new opportunities for innovation and value creation from climate data at national and European levels.

4 Conclusions

This deliverable concludes the demonstration and validation activities of WP5. All pilot demonstrators have been successfully deployed, integrated, and validated in their respective operational environments, confirming the maturity and flexibility of the DATAMITE framework.

The results demonstrate that DATAMITE can be effectively adapted to heterogeneous infrastructures, data domains, and organisational contexts, supporting both cloud-based and in-house deployments. The conducted validation campaigns confirm the correctness of the adopted architecture, the effectiveness of the CI/CD procedures, and the framework's readiness for exploitation beyond the project lifetime.

Overall, WP5 successfully demonstrated the applicability of the DATAMITE framework across multiple real-world pilots. Despite differences in technical setups and operational constraints, the demonstrators consistently validated the core design principles of the framework and its ability to support diverse use cases. The outcomes of WP5 provide a solid and reliable foundation for the further uptake and exploitation of DATAMITE results beyond the project.